

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DRATE****FIRST NAME: AKUBARU****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2 %

The author used the MS Word 2016 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Features of academic essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7)
2. Rule of styles (Cleenewerck 2016)
3. Divergences in US and British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34)
5. Latin abbreviations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 59-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL PAPER WRITING BASICS

1) INTRODUCTION

In 2019, I started submitting applications to different universities for Ph.D. admission. I was interested in a Ph.D. program offered online by an accredited university. Other than US, European, and Asian Universities, I could not come across an African-based University that offered an online Ph.D. program suiting my taste. A colleague introduced me to the online Ph.D. programs at the EUCLID after sharing my interest in pursuing an online Ph.D. program. EUCLID had yet to launch the Ph.D. in Epidemiology and Biostatistics. I applied for the Doctorate (Ph.D.) in Public Health and Health Systems and later requested to be changed to the Epidemiology and Biostatistics track when it became available.

I downloaded the prospectus for the university and noted as a student, I would start the program with the international academic methods course module. My deep dive to understand the course from the University website led me to realize the course covered international academic writing. I did not go to a nursery school, but I did take my studies using the English language as a medium of instruction. For a long time, I have thought of

myself as being fluent in English (both written and oral). I was wrong. Reading the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one coursepack (fourth edition), I realized I was still a long way in different aspects of my English skills for academic writing. In particular, I found the differences between US and British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25) set out in the coursepack new things to me. I should have paid more attention to these differences in writing.

In the subsequent sections, I discuss my opinions and reflections on the different aspects of academic writing presented in the course materials. In particular, I will focus on the characteristics of academic essays, rules of style, US and British English, plagiarism, Latin abbreviations, and paragraph styling.

2) FEATURES OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

I learned about essay writing fifteen years ago. Little did I know there were specific considerations to take in writing an essay for academic purposes. According to Cleenewerck and Gulma, different types of essays exist. As both noted:

Examples of academic writing include research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monograph; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).¹

Academic essays involve factual writing from scholarly works and convey messages based on evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). I have participated in several research activities and generated data for writing research reports, but I need more attention to these essays. I found the tips (including beginning early, staggering the writing, creating time between draft and review, proof-reading, and spell-checking) proposed by Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021 for compelling writing exciting (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11).

3) RULE OF STYLES

I found Prof. Cleenewerck's description of different rules of style (WHO, European Commission (EC), Oxford, Turabian, etc.) new to my understanding (Cleenewerck 2021). I have used MS Office for over twenty years of my career and am adept at inserting and updating tables of content. However, I have paid little attention to the differences between the styles and paragraphs. When I listened to the tutorial by Prof. Cleenewerck, I learned

¹ I did not know all the types mentioned here were treated as academic essays. For instance, technical reports, translation, and student presentations.

that one needs to download the guides from the internet (Cleenewerck 2016). Due to the learning, I successfully downloaded the Turabian In-Text style in my Zotero software.

Different organizations or institutions often want their employees to adhere to their branding, including a style guide. I always wondered why such organizations are particular in their directions and require adherence to the rules. As Cleenewerck and Gulma note:

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41).

I found the list of items considerable in style unusual as it appears long. However according to Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2021, it could be longer, depending on the publication, writer, and or company (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 42). I need to download the BBC News style guide to understand how the corporation treats its style. But my close examination of the Oxford style was an exciting experience.

4) US AND BRITISH ENGLISH

I studied in Uganda, where British English is predominant over US English. For a long time, I have believed that English Language is the same. But when I started working on projects funded by USAID and PEPFAR, I realized my managers directed my style towards US English. I have wondered about the difference between the two. I did not come across any training to re-purpose my English Language. This course has made me realize the difference, but it is insufficient to make one perfect in differentiating the two. Although the use of US English has expanded since World War II for various reasons, it remains more similar to British English than it is different (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). I found the variations in the two English Languages interesting in the following areas:

a) Periods, Commas, and Quotation Marks

Considering the difference between US and British English in applying periods, Commas, and Quotation Marks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31-32), I found using double and single quotes fascinating for the US and British English, respectively.

b) Punctuation with Business (Formal) vs. Social (Informal) Letters

During my childhood, the teachers taught us how to use punctuation and social letters without drawing students' attention to the different types of English Languages. I encountered several letters that writers addressed using different styles, and I never imagined the difference was due to the variations in the two variants of World English. The use of a full stop after "Mr" followed by a double full stop (:) for addressing a person in US English compared to only writing "Mr" without a full stop and followed by a comma for British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 32) is an important consideration.

It is important to note that the US and British English are more similar than they are different, and Authors should consider their differences in writing essays. One can set the proofing Language to either by selecting all the text, navigating to the Review tab, or clicking the Language drop-down arrow (Cleenewerck 2016).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism occurs when a writer does not acknowledge or cite the source or sources of information he has used (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021, 34), plagiarism is harmful and should be avoided, adding that it is "wrong and unethical" and "is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences." I heard about Plagiarism over six years ago, but I did not know the tools for measuring it. My interaction with the tutorial on the basics of Grammarly helped me to understand how one can determine the level of Plagiarism in one's writing. I have noted that before submitting RPs, each student must subject their work to a Plagiarism check and report the percentage. I have also found the Grammarly application helpful in running checks on the correctness of sentences, punctuations, words, and other aspects of writing.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

Latin abbreviations are essential, but to avoid being misinterpreted, one should use the English equivalent (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59). Although Latin Abbreviations exist with their English counterparts, I have yet to pay attention to the meaning of many. Latin abbreviations such as pro rata, pro bono, per capita, and ad hoc (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 63) appear frequently in written essays. People can quickly treat the abbreviations as if they were English words. It is essential to take precautions and use their English equivalents to ensure every reader of the essay understands them the same.

7)CONCLUSION

Academic writing is more than adhering to the essentials of essay writing. It also involves the application of style guides, proper composition of sentences and use of punctuations, citation of works of others, and adherence to the type of English to use. I am motivated to work hard to succeed in the program. There is more to learn than known, and I can only attain perfection through practice.

The coursepack and video tutorials were very informative and availing them during the program was very helpful in understanding the basics of academic writing and using the templates. They remain relevant references as I use their concepts to improve my writing skills.

The video tutorial by Prof. Cleenewerck on the use of styles in MS Word and format documents provided critical hands-on guidance on using the response paper template, rules of style, and switching Language proofing from the US and British English Languages. The introductory tutorials on the use of Grammarly and Zotero and the Review of RPs by Dr. Gulma were very helpful in setting the ground for the course.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.